

EFFICIENCY OF TEACHING SCHOOLCHILDREN TO SOLVING OLYMPIAD PROBLEMS IN INFORMATICS

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Abstract

One of the directions of developing the abilities of talented youth is the organization of Olympiad work. The article discusses the tasks that organize the preparation of students for computer science Olympiads and arise before the teacher. Specialized Internet resources are available for conducting programming Olympiads and preparing participants for them. Tasks can be automated due to their large number and complexity, which, when performed manually, leads to a limitation of the actions of students in decision-making. The system of automatic verification of programming tasks was considered as a means of automating these tasks and improving the effectiveness of classes with students. Various variants of publicly available systems for automatic verification of programming tasks are analyzed (Yandex.Contest, acmp.ru (school of programmers), informatics.msk.ru (distance training in computer science) and their capabilities.

Keywords: programming, olympiad, the system of preparing students for the olympiad, creativity, stages of problem solving.

Preparing schoolchildren for participation in the Olympiads in connection with the revival of the Olympic movement, the problem of organizing the process is now becoming more and more urgent. Academic Olympiads are a kind of intellectual competition for students in a certain scientific field, which allows you to determine the degree of academic achievements of students, as well as to test the ability of students to use the knowledge gained in the process of solving tasks. Such Olympiads are held to identify and develop students' interest in scientific activities in order to popularize their creative abilities and scientific knowledge. Disciplinary Olympiads for schoolchildren are one of the most effective means of identifying the possibility and degree of assimilation of theoretical material. Such activities also help students develop their mental and creative abilities. Participation in subject Olympiads contributes to the development of students' abilities at a high level in accordance with the areas of training.

The organization of the process of preparing students for participation in the Olympiad begins with the preparation of the teacher himself. The main questions that the teacher faces in the process of preparing a student for the Olympiad:

- to teach the student to properly organize their activities for participation in the Olympiad;
- mastering the forms of these events;
- study of algorithms for solving problems offered to the participants of the Olympiad;
- ability to work with programming languages;
- time to learn and check the problems that students must solve at the Olympiads.

Studies have shown that the successful participation of a student in computer science olympiads guarantees the knowledge [1]:

- technical characteristics of computer equipment;
- the main functions of popular operating systems;
- main types of algorithms;

- the ability to make reports in one or more programming languages, directly approved by the organizers of the Olympiads.

In addition, a student directly participating in the Olympiad must have the following skills:

- work with modern computer equipment operating in modern operating systems, their programming systems;
- taking into account the established technical and content restrictions, the transition from the verbal formulation of tasks to their formal description;
- use of basic algorithms in practice;
- use of modern methods of repair and testing of software products.

An analysis of many years of experience allows us to conclude that the main problem in the process of preparing schoolchildren for participation in Olympiads is that the section "algorithmization and programming" of the course "informatics" allows students to learn only a small amount of material. on the topics indicated. This, in turn, leads to insufficient preparation of schoolchildren for Olympiads in Informatics.

The general preparation of students for participation in subject Olympiads includes the following activities:

- selection of talented students;
- testing to determine the level of training of students in computer science;
- development of skills to work with modern computer equipment;
- knowledge of one of the main programming languages;
- mastering the algorithms necessary for solving Olympic problems;
- study of various ways of solving known algorithms;
- analysis of the effectiveness of programs;
- study of methods for testing software products;
- development of ways to write and configure software products on a computer [2].

To solve the problems of high-quality training of students participating in Olympiads in Informatics, it is necessary to conduct additional classes in small groups of 3-6 people. When conducting a lesson, it is necessary to take into account the level of preparation of students.

In the process of preparing students for participation in subject Olympiads, many different teaching methods can be used. All these methods can be used by the teacher in extra classes. This allows students to effectively absorb the studied material in a shorter time. Practical classes to prepare students for participation in Olympiads in Informatics are held in small study groups. In group problem solving, active learning methods are often used, in particular, brainstorming. At the same time, team members express their ideas and thoughts to solve the tasks assigned to them. Typically, a brain attack is limited in time and does not exceed 3-5 minutes. The teacher writes each idea on the board. In the process of brainstorming, students cannot talk about the proposed solutions, about the tasks assigned to them. In the next step, the teacher makes a list of these ideas, on the basis of which, together with the group, evaluates each idea and prioritizes them. Self-study or homework based on practical tasks help students develop learning and research skills. Individual tasks are created for independent work, they differ in size, complexity, creative focus, deadlines.

To control the preparation of students, differentiated control methods are used (level tasks or additional tasks). Students can take part in Internet programming olympiads to conduct a boundary control of knowledge gained in the course of preparation for olympiads in computer science.

Therefore, this method of preparing schoolchildren for Olympiads in Informatics allows them to increase their creative potential. In addition, this allows you to effectively solve the problems of high-quality training of participants in the Olympiads and develop the talents of students in the education system.

Stages of solving Olympic problems in informatics:

- meaningful statement of the problem;
- read the terms of the contract;
- creation of an algorithm for solving the problem;
- software implementation of the algorithm;
- setting up and testing the program;
- send the solution for verification, calculations, analysis and verification of the results;
- general conclusion [3].

Let's highlight the stages of solving Olympic problems in informatics.

1. Meaningful statement of the problem. At this stage, it is recommended to create a dynamic scheme - in many cases it helps to restore the situation that actually occurred, makes it easier to understand the situation of the problem and find its solution. Here, when considering known and unknown quantities with students, consider them not only in a narrow topic, but also from an interdisciplinary point of view.

2. Read the terms of the obligation. The main goal of the teacher's work at this stage is to create a mathematical model of the initial design situation based on its solution together with students. We clearly separate the

assumptions on which the mathematical model is built, establish links that connect the results with the initial data. For the correct interpretation of these relationships, "system-forming" questions are used, the discussion of which should be accompanied by the most adequate transformation of the original model or diagram on the display.

3. Creation of an algorithm for solving the problem. At this stage, an algorithm is created, which includes the choice of the method for constructing the algorithm, the choice of the form of the algorithm, and the design of the algorithm itself. After discussing all the relationships in the group and understanding the existence and nature of relationships between concepts, students can relatively independently proceed to the creation of an algorithm for solving this problem.

4. Software implementation. Here we will discuss together possible options for solving this problem on a computer. It is recommended to try to solve the problem in different ways, comparing different options in terms of efficiency, simplicity and versatility.

5. Setting up and testing the program. Testing and debugging includes: individual work on setting up the syntax, setting up the semantics and logical structure of the program, analyzing test protocols and test results, and finalizing the program.

6. Sending the solution for verification, calculations, analysis and verification of the results.

7. Conclusion. At this stage, a joint analysis of various ways of solving the problem by students is carried out, substantiating the choice of an effective method for solving the problem using software for educational purposes. Depending on the level of training of students, the considered structure of the process of solving Olympic problems can be implemented in different modifications and at different levels of the teacher [4].

Many large IT companies are interested in finding new solutions for everyday computer problems, so they hold competitions to find talented people who like programming and related sciences. The largest such olympiads are Google Code Jam, Yandex. algorithm and ACM ICPC.

The Internet Olympiad in Informatics is an important educational event, its organization includes the creation of assignments taking into account the age level of students' educational readiness, the development of the rules for holding the Olympiad and summing up, providing the material and technical base.

When preparing students for Olympiads, the importance of using an information system for automated verification of solutions to programming problems can be emphasized. When preparing for the Olympiad, you can use the following sites: acmp.ru, informatics.msk.ru, codeforces.com, etc., where, on the one hand, there are many tasks of the Olympiad level, and on the other hand, the testing system for each student forms a rating score from the marks solutions. Codeforces is a site that hosts programming competitions. He is supported by a team of competitive programmers from ITMO University. The authors focus on developing students' interest in Olympic programming through participation in competitions.

In addition to sites with a built-in rating system (acmp.ru, stepik.org), you can use a number of Internet resources without it (for example, Yandex.Contest). The described competitive effect can be achieved by introducing your own rating system in the classroom. This can be done using a specialized resource, or you can save a simple spreadsheet in any office product (including cloud services). You can also use the gamification resources of the educational process, where each participant is rewarded for the solved task. In this case, one can take into account not only the fact of the decision, but also the ability of the student to defend this decision and explain it to others.

Currently, programming tasks are present in many Olympiads for schoolchildren in computer science. In addition, the solution of such a problem consists not only in obtaining a program that works correctly for any input data, but also in making it efficient both in terms of implementation time and memory consumption.

There are various online resources for checking solutions to programming problems. Essentially, these resources play two roles. On the one hand, these are collections of programming tasks on various topics. On the other hand, when registering on these sites, the user has the opportunity to send solutions to these problems to the server. These solutions are checked by the automatic check system installed and configured on the server. The result of checking the solution is returned to the user. Such sites usually allow you to keep a history of submitted solutions for each problem. M.B. Rubtsova and Yu.V. Isakova's publication mentions one of these services, Yandex.Competition. In this system, there is no way to solve any specific problem. All programming problems are grouped into "competitions" and the problem can be solved only by joining the problems in which it is registered [5].

A method for automated generation of tests for Olympic programming problems is proposed to identify inefficient solutions. This method is based on the use of genetic algorithms. The use of the proposed methodology for creating new tests for the Olympic task from the Internet archive - acm.timus.ru is described. Holding competitions at a high level requires high-quality preparation of tasks. This process includes selecting interesting ideas for future tasks, writing conditions and solutions, and creating tests. This paper presents a new way to build an automated test for inefficient solutions - such solutions always have the correct answer, but some tests do not meet time or memory constraints.

In the case of a task, some restrictions are imposed on the input data. However, for many problems, it is not possible to check the solution in all possible tests that satisfy these restrictions, since the number of such tests is too large. Because of this, of all possible tests, you should choose only those that allow you to determine whether some solution is correct. However, according to Rice's theorem, this problem cannot be solved algorithmically in the general case. Therefore, it is possible to choose a set of tests that allow, to a certain extent, to confirm the correctness of the solution. The purpose of test preparation is to make this reliability as high as possible.

Nowadays, in the age of rapid development of technology, there are many extra-curricular self-improvement tools or online platforms for students. For example, acmp.ru (a set of programming problems for new initiatives), leetcode.com (a set of algorithmic programming problems), codeforces.com (Olympiad problems and solutions of various levels), habr.ru (a discussed platform and -answer format arising from tools informatics).

Let's look at the methods of effective preparation of Olympiad problems in computer science.

1. Staircase

Sanjar builds a ladder out of cubes. The staircase consists of several cubic towers built side by side, each one exactly one cube higher than the previous one. To determine what will be the height of the final staircase in cubes, it is necessary by the number of cubes.

Input data

The input file INPUT.TXT contains the number K , the number of cubes ($1 \leq K \leq 106$) in the array.

Output data

In the output file OUTPUT.TXT print the number of cubes on the last rung of the maximum possible ladder that can be built from K cubes.

Examples:

No	INPUT.TXT	OUTPUT.TXT
1	1	1
2	4	2
3	6	3

Solution:

To solve this problem, you need to calculate the height of the largest staircase that can be built from K cubes. To build a staircase of the greatest height, it is necessary to add as many cubes as possible to the current step at each step. If the maximum number of cubes cannot be added in the next step, the current step is the last one.

The algorithm for solving this problem can be described as follows:

1. Read the number of cubes from the input file and enter it into the variable K .
2. Set the number of steps to 1 in the stair variable.
3. Set the number of cubes to 1 in the cubes variable.
4. If the number of dice is less than or equal to K , do the following:
 4. Add value to the ladder together.

4. Add the number of steps to the number of cubes.
5. Output minus one of the value of the stairs.

As a result of the algorithm, we print the ladder minus one value. After all, the staircase does not actually include the number of steps, but the height of the last step at the exit from the contour. To get the number of steps, you need to subtract one from the value of the steps.

An example implementation of the algorithm in Python:

```
K = int(input())
stair = 1
cubes = 1
while cubes <= K:
    stair += 1
    cubes += stair
print(stair - 1)
```

2. Arithmetic progression

The first and second elements of an arithmetic progression are given. It is necessary to write a program that calculates the element of the progression by its number.

Input data

The first line of the input file INPUT.TXT contains three space-separated integers: A1 is the first element of the progression ($1 \leq A1 \leq 1000$), A2 is the second element of the progression ($1 \leq A2 \leq 1000$) and the required element is N ($1 \leq N \leq 1000$).

Output data

The output file OUTPUT.TXT must contain one integer - the Nth element of the arithmetic progression.

Examples:

№	INPUT.TXT	OUTPUT.TXT
1	1 5 3	9

Let's explain an example

Here we are talking about the following sequence of numbers:

1, 5, 9, 13, 17, 21, ...

In this scheme, $D=4$, so $A1=1$, $A2=A1+D=5$, $A3=A1+2*D=9$, etc. Since we need to find the 3rd element of the progression, the answer to the problem is 9.

Solution:

1. Read the input data from the INPUT.TXT file. To do this, you can use the `input()` function or the more convenient `open()` function:

```
with open('INPUT.TXT', 'r') as input_file:
    data = input_file.readline().split()
    a1 = int(data[0])
    a2 = int(data[1])
    n = int(data[2])
```

2. Find the progression difference d as the difference between the second and first elements:

$$d = a2 - a1$$

3. Find the n - element of the progression as the product of the sum of the first element and the difference $(n-1)$:

$$an = a1 + d * (n - 1)$$

4. We write the result to the output file:

```
with open('OUTPUT.TXT', 'w') as output_file:
    output_file.write(str(an))
```

The result is the complete code:

with `open('INPUT.TXT', 'r')` as `input_file`:

```
data = input_file.readline().split()
```

```
a1 = int(data[0])
```

```
a2 = int(data[1])
```

```
n = int(data[2])
```

```
d = a2 - a1
```

```
an = a1 + d * (n - 1)
```

with `open('OUTPUT.TXT', 'w')` as `output_file`:

```
output_file.write(str(an))
```

Another solution:

```
a1, a2, n = map(int, input().split())
```

```
d = a2 - a1
```

```
an = a1 + (n-1)*d
```

```
print(an)
```

3. Arrival time

Given the time of departure of the train and the time of arrival at the last station. You need to write a program to find the arrival time (perhaps on a different day) of this train.

Input data

The input file INPUT.TXT contains two lines. The first line is the departure time, the second is the travel time. The output time is specified in the format "HH:MM", where HH is the time in hours, takes a value from 00 to 23, MM is the time in minutes, takes a value from 00 to 59. The second travel time is given. The two non-negative integers are the number of hours and minutes. Numbers are separated by one space. The number of hours does not exceed 120, minutes - 59.

Output data:

The output file OUTPUT.TXT should contain one line - the time the train arrived at the last station. The output format for this time is the same as the format for the departure time.

Examples:

№	INPUT.TXT	OUTPUT.TXT
1	00:00 10 10	10:10
2	01:02 4 6	05:08
3	11:00 22 0	09:00

Solution:

To solve the problem, you must first analyze the departure time and travel time for hours and minutes, then add them, taking into account the possible overflow of minutes and hours, and display the result.

Let's do it step by step:

1. Read data from the INPUT.TXT file. The first line shows the departure time in HH:MM format, the second line shows the travel time in hours and minutes, separated by spaces.

2. Divide the departure time into hours and minutes using the `split(":")` method.

3. Let's translate the departure time and travel time into minutes. To do this, multiply the hours by 60 and add the minutes.

4. Add the departure time in minutes and the travel time in minutes to get the arrival time in minutes.

5. If the arrival time is the next day, we will calculate the number of days to extend the trip. To do this,

we check that the arrival time is greater than 1440 (the number of minutes in a day), and calculate the number of days to be added to the departure date.

6. Calculate the time of arrival in the format "HH:MM". To do this, divide the remaining arrival time in minutes by 60 to get the number of minutes in hours, and subtract the number of minutes from the arrival time to get the number of hours. If the number of hours is less than 10, add a leading zero to it.

7. If you need to add a date, enter the arrival date in the format "DD:HH:MM", where DD is the number of days, HH is the number of hours, MM is the number of minutes. Otherwise, we will display the arrival time only in the format "HH:MM".

Write the result to the OUTPUT.TXT file.

Solution code in Python:

```
with open('INPUT.TXT', 'r') as input_file:
    departure_time = input_file.readline().strip()
    travel_time = input_file.readline().strip()

# split the send time into hours and minutes
departure_hours, departure_minutes = map(int,
departure_time.split(':'))

# dividing travel time into hours and minutes
travel_hours, travel_minutes = map(int,
travel_time.split())

# calculate the total time in minutes
total_minutes = departure_hours * 60 +
departure_minutes + travel_hours * 60 +
travel_minutes

# calculate arrival hours and minutes
arrival_hours = total_minutes // 60 % 24
arrival_minutes = total_minutes % 60

# arrival time output format
arrival_time =
'{:02d}:{:02d}'.format(arrival_hours,
arrival_minutes)
```

write the result to a file

with open('OUTPUT.TXT', 'w') as output_file:
output_file.write(arrival_time)

Summing up, the article reveals the content and methodological features of the organization of work to solve the Olympic problems, gives its methodological characteristics. As our experience shows, the introduction of the proposed pedagogical solutions significantly increases the efficiency of students' mastering the skills of solving Olympiad problems in computer science, thereby realizing the developing potential of the programming course at various stages and levels of education.

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